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Chasing Fish: 130 Years of Innovation, Displacement and Depletion in Scottish Fisheries

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Correspondence: Zoe F. J. Heard (zh263@exeter.ac.uk)**Received:** 22 April 2025 | **Revised:** 29 October 2025 | **Accepted:** 8 December 2025**Keywords:** catchability | fisheries management | gear development | historical ecology | technological creep

ABSTRACT

Rebuilding the depleted fisheries of the 21st century requires an understanding of past drivers of their decline. Despite Scotland's central role in the commercial exploitation of North Sea fisheries for over a century, associations between technological innovations, regulatory introductions and fishery landings have not previously been quantified. Here we use data from annual Scottish Government fisheries reports (1890–2020) to examine these associations. Traditional passive fishing gears were displaced by mobile gears in distinct phases across the demersal, pelagic and shellfish sectors, with increases in landings recorded for variable periods. Demersal line fishers were displaced by trawlers from 1899, pelagic drift netters were superseded by pelagic trawlers and purse-seiners from 1963, and shellfish creels were succeeded by trawlers targeting *Nephrops norvegicus* from 1964. The widespread adoption of steam propulsion (late 19th/early 20th century), motor propulsion and ancillary technologies, for example, echosounders (mid-20th century) further increased the power of fishing fleets. The sequential transition from passive to active and more environmentally damaging gears across all major fishery sectors (demersal, pelagic and shellfish) respectively indicates intensification of fishing effort for lower trophic levels, with increasing impacts upon marine ecosystems. Technological progress was facilitated by governing bodies over the 20th century through loans and subsidies. Efforts to curtail fishing effort were then reactive to declines in fish stocks from the latter-20th century. This century-long perspective demonstrates how technological innovations can swiftly be adopted with subsequent adverse ecological consequences, and highlights the importance of pre-emptively managing innovations to enhance fisheries sustainability, rather than drive declines.

1 | Introduction

It is widely accepted in the scientific community that fisheries, and marine biodiversity more broadly, are in decline globally as a result of technical progress and associated increased fishing power (i.e., the efficiency of fish catching by vessels), overcapacity, increasing environmental invasiveness of gears and habitat degradation—ultimately driven by rising demand for seafood from growing populations (Eigaard et al. 2014; Pauly et al. 2002; Pontecorvo and Schrank 2012; Sala and Knowlton 2006; Squires and Vestergaard 2013).

Technological developments and changes to fishing power in North Sea and North Atlantic fisheries have been covered in the literature, and studies highlight general trends of increasing catching power of vessels over extended time periods (Eigaard et al. 2014; Engelhard 2008, 2016; Garstang 1900; Jones et al. 2015; Kerby et al. 2012; Mahévas et al. 2011; Marchal et al. 2007; Palomares and Pauly 2019; Standal 2005). Across the 19th and into the 20th century, incremental improvements in gear and vessel design, termed technological creep (Palomares and Pauly 2019), included the building of larger vessels, increases in the length of lines, number of fishing hooks and sizes

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of nets used, the adoption of steam and latterly motor power, the invention of power winches, improved fish storage and processing and the strengthening of nets and lines through use of synthetic fibres (e.g., monofilament) (Eigaard et al. 2014; Hunt et al. 2024; Kerby et al. 2012; Payne et al. 2009; Scherrer and Galbraith 2020b).

In the short term, increased catch capabilities facilitated increases in landings (Engelhard 2008). However, when fisheries technology outpaces the replenishment of commercial fish stocks, to compensate for declining catch per unit effort, further improvements in technology, geographical expansion of fishing effort and fishery diversification are required to maintain profitability (Abernethy et al. 2010; Engelhard 2016) in a technological arms race for fish (Longo et al. 2015; Symes 2001). For example, declines in targeted fish stocks due to intensive fishing pressure by traditional gears incentivised the development of increasingly effective gears, such as bottom trawls and seine nets, and the adoption of fish-finding technology, to increase fishing efficiency and capitalise on depleted remaining and previously untargeted stocks (Day 1969; Payne et al. 2009; Roberts 2007; Whitmarsh et al. 1995).

Repercussions of the development of increasingly effective and environmentally invasive fishing gears on the marine environment are varied and vast. For example, the act of dragging fishing gears across the seabed is known to reduce benthic structural complexity and marine biodiversity, and leads to the destruction or near total loss of important and vulnerable habitats (e.g., biogenic reefs) which act as key feeding, spawning and nursery areas for a wide range of species, including commercially valuable fish stocks (Engelhard 2016; Hall-Spencer and Moore 2000; Stewart and Howarth 2016; Thurstan et al. 2024). Trawling and dredging of the seabed also disturbs buried organic carbon, leading to CO₂ being re-released into the ocean and the atmosphere with widespread repercussions for ocean acidification and the global climate (Atwood et al. 2024; Porz et al. 2024). Seine netting also leads to high bycatch rates of non-target and immature fish owing to the mesh of nets narrowing during hauling (Jones 2016; Le Floc'h et al. 2023; Rihan et al. 2016; Walsh and Winger 2011), and to incidental entanglement and catch of marine mammals and seabirds (Gislason 1994; Read et al. 2006). Furthermore, the adoption of naval technologies after the World Wars, for example, echosounders/fish finders and GPS and the development of motor engines increased the reach of vessels, allowed precise identification of shoals of fish, and reduced the areas that were once de facto refuges from fishing activity (Holm 2012; Montgomerie 2022; Valdemarsen 2001; Watling and Norse 1998).

While advancing fishing power in North Sea fisheries has been described, associations among technological advances, changing fishery characteristics and fish landings are less studied. The recording of British fisheries statistics by fisheries authorities since the latter stages of the Industrial Revolution presents an opportunity to examine these associations over the course of more than a century, during which our ability to catch fish was transformed.

British fishing industries became an early beneficiary of the Industrial Revolution (c.1760–1850) as improved standards of living made fish more affordable, rapid human population

growth led to increased demand, railways allowed efficient transportation of fresh fish from coasts to inland markets, and the introduction of steam power expanded and intensified fishing operations (Kerby et al. 2012; Knauss 2005). These favourable economic and technological developments led to the United Kingdom pioneering industrial, commercial fishery exploitation on the European continental shelf, namely the North Sea and North Atlantic (Kerby et al. 2012).

While English fleets shifted focus away from the North Sea to profitable distant waters from the early 20th century, Scotland continued to fish local grounds and became the centre of the UK's fishery sector (Day 1969; Hatcher and Read 2001; Kerby et al. 2012). Increased seafood demand and expanding fishing fleets from neighbouring European nations, in particular, Denmark, Norway and the Soviet Union, fuelled developments to fishing technology in Scotland to increase catches and remain competitive (Kerby et al. 2012). Scotland, therefore, serves as an ideal case-study to explore the impact of technological advancement on North Sea/North Atlantic fisheries. We examine the progressive introduction and substitution of fishing gears, and investigate associations between innovations and landings, using historical Scottish Government fisheries landings data by method of catch between 1890 and 2020. We highlight rapid and transformational shifts from passive gears (i.e., dependent on the movement of target species towards the gear) to active gears (i.e., gears that chase target species) across multiple fishery sectors, and show how the timing of these shifts coincided with transitions in propulsion methods. To better understand and interpret fisheries trends, consideration was also given to the increased mobility of fishing fleets, the introduction of ancillary technologies, notable ecological events (e.g., the gadoid outburst—a period over which key commercial demersal fish produced exceptionally large year classes [Engelhard et al. 2014]), political events (e.g., war), and policy introductions. With these data, we characterise how Scottish fisheries responded to gear innovations, key ecological/political events and governance efforts over the course of 130 years, ultimately so that fisheries could remain productive and economically viable.

2 | Sources & Methods

Fisheries landings data were acquired from digitised Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistics annual reports available from the 'ProQuest U.K. Parliamentary Papers' online repository for years 1890–1921 (UK Parliamentary Papers, n.d.) and the Scottish Government website for years 1922–2020 (Sea Fisheries Statistics 1922–2010 2011). These reports were designed to oversee fishing operations in Scotland and documented the weight and value of fisheries landings (by species and gear type) and fleet/employment statistics (Table 1). Information for these reports was sourced from fisher logbooks, which were made mandatory, and vessel registration/licencing data, and were compiled on an annual basis.

We extracted and compiled annually resolved pelagic, demersal and shellfish landings data by method of catch (gear type), by method of propulsion (sail/steam/motor) and species-specific landings from the reports. For the list of species targeted and their categorisation, see Appendix S1. Landings were recorded in

metric tonnes from 1975; prior to these dates various conversion factors were used to standardise the dataset (Table 1). Landing weights represent the head on gutted fish weight for demersal species and whole ungutted fish weight for pelagics and shellfish. For descriptions of the fishing methods used, including how they operate to catch fish, see Appendix S2. Landings data by method of fishing propulsion (i.e., sail/steam/motor) were available for 1890–1976 for steam powered pelagic and demersal fisheries landings, and from 1906 to 1938 and 1953 to 1976 for sail and motor powered pelagic and demersal landings, after which all landings were made by motor vessels (Table 1). See Appendix S3 for the reported number of sail, steam and motor vessels from 1890 to 2020. The narrative section of the reports provided contextual information on fisheries technological developments, the imposition of regulations, and political and ecological conditions influencing Scottish fisheries landings (Table 1); this information was extracted and tabulated in the results.

2.1 | Data Limitations

Landings by method of catch data were not recorded from 1995 to 1999 due to changes in reporting style (Table 1), corresponding to the period during which the UK devolved fisheries management responsibilities to Scotland in 1998. Shellfish landings by method of catch data were not recorded systematically until 1978; however, *Nephrops* (*Nephrops norvegicus*) trawl and shellfish landings by seine-nets were recorded from 1954. Up to 1978, we used crab and lobster landings as a proxy for total creel landings, and the remaining shellfish landings up to 1978 were recorded under ‘miscellaneous’ methods. Demersal and pelagic landings by method of catch were consistently reported, but small quantities of landings were recorded as landed by ‘miscellaneous’ nets, with no further explanation as to what these were.

Scottish crab, lobster and oyster landings were recorded by number of individuals landed up until 1975 when landing weights were standardised to metric tonnes (Table 1). We made assumptions on which species were historically landed based on more recent, species-specific records (from 1975) and calculated conversion factors based on average adult weights of these species (Table 1). These results can only be interpreted as estimations of landings (by weight) due to size and seasonal variability, and as it is probable that landings consisted of different species of crab/lobster/oyster with different average weights. Species-specific pelagic, demersal and shellfish landings were recorded consistently; however, small (unknown) quantities of ‘other’ species were recorded in the reports, with no information as to which species were included in these categories likely due to their minimal commercial value.

3 | Results

3.1 | An Overview of Events Impacting Scottish Fisheries Landings

During the period of analysis, Scottish fishing industries were shaped by continuous technological advancement and evolving regulatory frameworks that interacted to transform fishing

capacity, efficiency and sustainability (Table 2). Scottish fisheries sectors progressed from using sail-powered boats and traditional preservation methods (e.g., salting/curing) in the early/mid-19th century to using larger, decked steam-powered vessels, mobile fishing gears (e.g., beam and latterly otter trawls), ice storage and rail transport by the early 1900s. Together, these allowed for increased fishing capacity, expansion of fishing range and improved fish storage and transport to reach growing markets (Table 2). The post WW2 era saw a shift from labour-intensive to technology-driven fishing, facilitated by the motorisation of fishing vessels, mechanical fish hauling, stronger synthetic nets and lines, adoption of fish detection technology and eventually the introduction of industrial-scale demersal and pelagic trawlers with on-board fish freezing and processing (Table 2). These advancements led to improved fish targeting, larger hauls, further expansion of fishing grounds and increased length of fishing trips. In the late 20th and early 21st centuries, technological advances were geared towards improved monitoring of fishing activity (using vessel tracking systems) and improvements to gear selectivity (Table 2).

Regulatory developments initially promoted and latterly closely followed technological advances. The 1868 Sea Fisheries Act, the 1889 Herring Fishery Act, the 1909 Trawling in Prohibited Areas Prevention Act and the 1933 Sea Fishing Industry Act aimed to stimulate growth in fishing capacity through initial removal of restrictions, then introduction of grants and loans and protective measures to conserve commercially valuable fish stocks (e.g., technical gear measures to prevent overfishing of juvenile fish and closed areas to destructive gear types) (Table 2). Post 1970 policy frameworks, such as the establishment of Total Allowable Catches (TACs), the 1983 EU Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), vessel decommissioning schemes and monitoring systems, sought to address overexploitation of stocks (Table 2).

3.2 | Trends in Scottish Fisheries

Scotland’s fishing industries went through notable changes in structure on account of resource availability, market demand and regulation. They transitioned from a strong dependency on pelagic fish to demersal fish for a short period and then back to pelagic fish, with the shellfish industry also growing in the latter 20th and early 21st centuries (Figure 1a). Passive gears, that is, drift nets, lines and creels consistently contributed the majority (73.1%) of Scottish landings until 1945. Following this, mobile gears took precedence and were responsible for 89.1% of landings from 1946 until the end of the reported time series (Figure 1b).

The pelagic drift netting sector landed more fish than any other gear type from 1890 to 1955, except during WW1 when fishing of North Sea herring grounds was curtailed (Figure 1b). From the 1950s landings via this method declined and, by the 1980s, recorded landings by drift nets had collapsed. Pelagic landings were maintained and increased in quantity again from the 1960s as ring nets, purse seines and pelagic trawls were introduced; purse seines and pelagic trawls contributed most to Scottish landings from 1981 to 1994 and 2000 to 2020 respectively

TABLE 1 | Sources and types of quantitative and qualitative data extracted to describe changes to Scotland's fisheries between 1890 and 2020.

Source	Years	Quantitative data	Conversion factors	Qualitative data
9th–46th Annual Report of the Fishery Board of Scotland, Sea Fisheries-Statistical Tables	1890–1927	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic and demersal landings by method of catch. Landings by method of propulsion (sail/steam/motor).	1 cwt = 0.0508 t 1 cran = 0.1778 t (Waterman 1964) 1 lobster (<i>Homarus gammarus</i>) = 0.0007 t (http://www.orkneylobsterhatchery.co.uk/lobsters.html) 1 (average adult) brown crab (<i>Cancer pagurus</i>) = 0.0006 t (Woll and Ålesund 2006) 1 native oyster (<i>Ostrea edulis</i>) = 0.00015 t (https://www.martin.ac.uk/species/detail/1146)	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Historical political/ecological events. Imposition of fishing regulations.
Fishery Board for Scotland, Sea Fisheries-Statistical Tables	1928–1938	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic and demersal landings by method of catch. Landings by method of propulsion (sail/steam/motor).	1 cwt = 0.0508 t 1 cran = 0.1778 t 1 lobster = 0.0007 t 1 crab = 0.0006 t 1 oyster = 0.00015 t	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Historical political/ecological events. Imposition of fishing regulations.
Scottish Home Department, Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistical Tables	1939–1958	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic, demersal and <i>Nephrops</i> (from 1954) landings by method of catch. Landings by method of propulsion (sail/steam/motor).	1 cwt = 0.0508 t 1 cran = 0.1778 t 1 lobster = 0.0007 t 1 crab = 0.0006 t 1 oyster = 0.00015 t	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Historical political/ecological events. Imposition of fishing regulations.
Department of Agriculture and Fisheries for Scotland, Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistical Tables	1959–1988	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic, demersal and shellfish (from 1978) landings by method of catch. Landings by method of propulsion (sail/steam/motor) up to 1976 (after which, all landings were from motorised vessels).	1 cwt = 0.0508 t 1 cran = 0.1778 t 1 lobster = 0.0007 t 1 crab = 0.0006 t 1 oyster = 0.00015 t	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Historical political/ecological events. Imposition of fishing regulations. Descriptions of fishing methods (from 1976).

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Source	Years	Quantitative data	Conversion factors	Qualitative data
The Scottish Office. Agriculture and Fisheries Department. Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistical Tables	1989–1997	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic, demersal and shellfish landings by method of catch.	n/a—data were recorded in metric tonnes	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Imposition of fishing regulations. Descriptions of fishing methods (up to 1995).
Scottish Executive. Rural Affairs Department. Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistics	1998–1999	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic, demersal and shellfish landings by method of catch (not recorded between 1995 and 1999).	n/a—data were recorded in metric tonnes	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Imposition of fishing regulations.
Scottish Fisheries Statistics	2000–2007	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic, demersal and shellfish landings by method of catch.	n/a—data were recorded in metric tonnes	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Imposition of fishing regulations.
A National Statistics Publication for Scotland. Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistics	2008–2011	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic, demersal and shellfish landings by method of catch.	n/a—data were recorded in metric tonnes	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Imposition of fishing regulations.
Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistics. Marine Scotland	2012–2020	Species-specific landings data. Pelagic, demersal and shellfish landings by method of catch.	n/a—data were recorded in metric tonnes	Introduction of fishing gears and ancillary technologies. Imposition of fishing regulations.

Note: Conversion factors used to standardise the fisheries landings data are given.

TABLE 2 | Key technological advancements, policy introductions and fishing incentives and ecological/political events influencing Scottish fishery landings.

Time-period	Influence	Descriptor	Reasoning
1800–1850	Technology (Vessel/processing)	Sail fishing boats (small, undecked)	Limited technology prior to industrialisation. Fish cured/salted to preserve for markets.
1850–70	Technology (Distribution)	Expansion of rail network	Opened up new, urban markets for local fisheries landings. Facilitated fishery expansion in Scotland.
1868	Policy (Incentive)	UK Sea Fisheries Act	Deregulated all fishing activity. Focus placed on developing and improving efficiency of the fleets.
1860–1870	Technology (Vessel)	Larger, decked boats built- able to travel further offshore	Increased fishing capacity. Growing populations, rising demand, need to source and supply more fish.
1882	Policy (Regulation)	Fishery Board of Scotland established	Centralised regulation, management and oversight of fishing operations in Scotland. Produced annual fishery reports.
1882–1898	Technology (Vessel/gear)	Steam beam trawlers and liners (demersal boats), steam drifters (pelagic boats) and steam capstans introduced	Increased fishing capacity. Steam powered vessels not as dependent on weather and sea conditions as sailing vessels- able to travel further offshore and in poor weather conditions, and fish around the clock. Mechanised hauling of fishing nets.
1889	Policy (Regulation)	Herring Fishery (Scotland) Act. 3-mile fishing limit introduced for bottom trawlers	Aimed to regulate and protect Scotland's herring fisheries. Inshore waters protected from steam trawling activity.
1890	Technology (Processing)	Development of ice houses in major Scottish fishing ports	Improved profitability of fisheries. Extended fish storage life, eliminated need for curing/salting.
1895–1900	Technology (Gear)	Adoption of otter trawl, replacing beam trawl	Increased fishing capacity. Otter boards replaced large, heavy beam, facilitated use of larger nets, could be used on rockier terrain.
1909	Technology (Gear)	First motors fitted onto sailing vessels	Increased fishing capacity. Greater towing power, extended fishing range, not as reliant on weather conditions.
1909	Policy (Regulation)	Trawling in Prohibited Areas Prevention Act	Prohibited the use of trawling gears in inshore waters and nursery/spawning grounds to conserve fish stocks and to prevent conflict with line/net fishers.
1910	Technology (Processing)	Local ice factories developed/mechanical chilling	Improved fishing profitability. Preserved quality of fish for transport to central markets.

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Time-period	Influence	Descriptor	Reasoning
1914–1918	Political event	WW1	Fishing restricted. Chief market connections cut off, fishing areas curtailed, most vessels chartered for Naval services, most fishers joined naval/military forces.
1921	Technology (Gear)	Danish seine net fishing technique adopted	Increased fishing capacity. Efficient, low-cost alternative to trawling for demersal species (well suited for smaller boats and used less fuel).
1924	Policy (Incentive)	Loans given to fishers	Capacity enhancement. Scottish Government made loans available to fishers for purchasing or improving vessels/gears.
1931	Technology (Ancillary)	Air Ministry service aircraft used to search for shoals of pelagic fish	Improved fishing efficiency. Identification of location of pelagic fish to reduce time searching, reduce fuel costs and increase catches.
1933	Policy (Regulation/incentive)	Sea Fishing Industry Act	Regulated the UK's fishing industry. Prohibited landing of undersized, immature fish; introduced closed areas/times; prescribed quotas for foreign countries; restricted imports; increased grants and loans to modernise vessels and improve efficiency.
1936–1938	Technology (Ancillary)	Instillation of electrical aids: electric lighting, electric winches, depth sounders, wireless telephones, navigational aids	Shift from labour-intensive to technology-driven fishing. Ancillary technologies allowed for improved crew safety, communication, fish finding and fishing efficiency.
1939–1945	Political event	WW2	Fishing restricted. Most fishers served in the navy, vessels requisitioned for war service, fishing grounds curtailed, market connections cut off.
1946	Technology (Processing)	Quick-freezing technology. Filleting and freezing fish at sea/in fish processing plants	Increased efficiency and profitability. Stabilised the market (evened out supplies and stabilised prices). Export market expanded (fish could be shipped overseas in good condition).
1948	Policy (Regulation)	Fisheries authorities began licencing vessels	To address concerns of overfishing/overcapacity.
1952	Policy (Regulation)	Iceland extended fishery limits to 12-miles offshore	Fishing restricted. Valuable fishing grounds for Scottish vessels cut off.

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Time-period	Influence	Descriptor	Reasoning
1950s/1960s	Technology (Ancillary)	Widespread transition to motor power; adoption of hydraulic winch hauling; echosounders used for 'visual trawling'; synthetic (nylon) twine developed	Increased fishing capacity/efficiency. Fishing grounds expanded and covered more efficiently; fishing gear fibres improved; larger nets could be used due to improved mechanical hauling.
1960s	Technology (Processing)	Industrial-scale processing lines and fish processing hubs developed	Increased profitability. Growth of frozen fish product export.
1960s	Technology (Gear)	Purse-seine and pelagic trawling methods introduced	Increased pelagic fishing capacity. More efficient method of catching fast swimming pelagic fish than otter trawling, allowed for use of bigger nets.
1962	Policy (Incentive)	Sea Fish Industry Act	Capacity enhancement. Provided industry subsidies and grants/loans to fishers, including for large vessels (> 140ft) and freezer trawlers.
1964	Policy (Regulation)	12-mile fishing limits established for coastal states	Conservation of local fish stocks. Aimed to reduce overfishing of nearshore waters; UK vessels given preferential access, foreign fishing effort controlled.
1967	Policy (Incentive)	'Gold Haddock' trophy award created. Deep sea vessel subsidy scheme approved. Small meshed net fishing for industrial species permitted.	Capacity enhancement. Instilled competition among white-fishing vessels. Removed financial barriers to entry into the industry. Removal of technical gear regulations to allow expansion of fishing effort.
~1960–1980	Ecological phenomenon	'Gadoid outburst'	Exceptional demersal fish year classes; mass increase in fishing opportunity.
1970s	Technology (Gear)	Rockhopper gear introduced for trawlers	Increased fishing efficiency. Enabled trawlers to operate in previously inaccessible areas.
1971	Policy (Regulation)	Herring (North Sea) Licencing and Restriction on Landing orders	Herring fishing restricted- closed periods and catch limits introduced. Aimed to allow spawning populations to recover and to protect juveniles.
1974	Technology (Gear)	Pair-trawling method (for pelagic species) introduced from Spain	Increased catch efficiency. Allowed UK fishers to remain competitive with foreign fleets using these methods.
1975	Policy (Regulation)	NE Atlantic Fisheries Commission begin system of TACs, enforce seasonal closures and minimum mesh sizes.	Fishing restricted through catch limits and technical measures to prevent overfishing and allow fish stocks to recover.

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Time-period	Influence	Descriptor	Reasoning
1975	Technology (Vessel/processing)	Industrial trawling begins	Increased fishing capacity.
1977–1981/1983	Policy (Regulation)	Total ban on herring fishing for West Scotland and North Sea grounds	Large trawlers added to fleet, extended operations: on-board refrigeration and processing allowed for longer fishing trips. Herring fishing restricted in response to the collapse of herring stocks in 1970s.
1980s	Technology (Ancillary)	Echosounders, GPS and sonar systems widely adopted across fishing fleets	Improved fishing efficiency.
1980s	Technology (Gear)	Twin-rig trawling method (for shellfish/demersal species) introduced from Denmark	Fish detection, tracking and targeting improved. Increased fishing capacity.
1982	Policy (Regulation)	Extension of fishery limits (EEZs) to 200 nautical miles	Allowed for the use of two trawl nets simultaneously.
1983	Policy (Regulation)	EU CFP established, fishing quotas and TACs introduced	Conservation of local fish stocks. Aimed to reduce overfishing of nearshore waters, UK vessels given preferential access to local waters, controlled foreign fishing effort.
1984	Policy (Incentive)	Inshore Fishing (Scotland) Act 3-mile inshore fishing limit repealed	To control fishing effort, prevent overfishing, conserve fish stocks, ensure fair access to resources.
1989	Technology (Gear)	Suction dredge fishing adaptation introduced	Trawling allowed in inshore waters to increase (short-term) landings and profit. Increased shellfish fishing capacity. Efficient alternative to traditional hand gathering or mechanical dredging.
1990s	Technology (Marketing)	Computerised fish inventory	Increased profitability. Improved seafood export logistics
1991	Technology (Gear)	Twin <i>Nephrops</i> trawling introduced	Increased shellfish fishing capacity.
1994–1997	Policy (Regulation)	Vessel decommissioning schemes	Gear covered larger areas, facilitated higher catch rates.
2001			Reduced fishing capacity to allow recovery of whitefish stocks.
2003–2004			Removal of 165 demersal fishing vessels from the Scottish fleet.
1990/2012	Policy (Regulation)	Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS) made mandatory for > 15m vessels (1990s) and smaller vessels (2012)	To control/monitor fishing effort. Vessel positions tracked to monitor compliance with closed areas, recovery zones and fishing quotas.
2000	Policy (Regulation)	<i>Nephrops</i> quotas introduced	To control fishing effort.

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Time-period	Influence	Descriptor	Reasoning
2000	Technology (Gear)	Square mesh panels in demersal trawls made mandatory	Improved gear selectivity. Reduced impact on non-target species.
2000–2007	Stock collapse	North Sea cod stocks collapse	Overfishing and adverse environmental conditions led to collapse of spawning stock.
2003	Policy (Regulation)	Cod Recovery Zones created	To protect and rebuild depleted cod stocks in the North Sea/North Atlantic.
2008	Technology (Regulation)	Remote Electronic Monitoring (REM) of Scottish fishing vessels using vessel positioning systems, sensors, cameras	To monitor fishing operations (effort, catch, bycatch).

Source: Scottish sea fisheries reports (Table 1).

(Figure 1b). In the latter 19th century, demersal landings were taken mainly by lines; however, the trawling sector quickly gained momentum with landings by demersal (otter) trawls overtaking those of lines in 1899. Danish seine netting also quickly came to dominate the demersal fishing industry after the introduction of the method post-WW1, and from the 1960s to 70s yielded the majority of landings (Figure 1b). Seine net landings declined after 1990, contributing < 5% of total Scottish landings from 2000. Recorded shellfish landings were low across the time-series, with creels landing just 1.4% of all Scottish landings, but the rise of *Nephrops* trawling from the mid-20th century led to the increased importance of the shellfish industry, with *Nephrops* trawlers landing on average 3.5% of all Scottish landings from the 1960s (Figure 1b).

3.3 | Pelagic Fishing Gears

From 1890 to 1962, drift nets were responsible for 96.5% of total pelagic landings, catching mostly herring (Figure 2). Up to 1907, the pelagic fleet was powered predominantly by sail, and then up to 1959 by steam (Figure 2a, Appendix S3). Despite the widespread adoption of steam power, drift net landings fluctuated on a downwards trajectory (Figure 2a). Landings by mobile gears gained momentum from the mid-1950s, coinciding with the widespread adoption of motor power, and overtook drift net landings from 1963 to 2020; pelagic trawls contributed 62.9% of landings, purse seiners 29%, ring nets 3.6%, and pair-trawls and miscellaneous nets each contributed 0.9% over this period, targeting mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), herring and sprats (*Sprattus sprattus*) (Figure 2a). Purse seine landings superseded ring net landings in 1967 (ring net landings declined precipitously from 1980) and pelagic trawl landings from 1978 to 1994, after which purse seine landings declined sharply (Figure 2a). Pelagic trawl landings then dominated again from 2000 to 2020, taking 95.3% of all pelagic landings, targeting herring, mackerel and blue whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*) (Figure 2).

3.3.1 | Pelagic Fisheries

Between 1890 and 1907, pelagic landings increased by 59.7%, from ~200,000 to ~300,000t (Figure 2). Landings of herring then began to decline, perpetuated by the near cessation of fishing during the World Wars. Following WW2, overall landings increased and targeted species soon included sprats and mackerel (Figure 2b).

Herring fishing restrictions were first introduced in 1971, under the Herring (North Sea) Licencing and Restriction on Landing orders; a total ban on herring fishing in the North Sea followed in 1977 (Figure 2b). Herring landings exhibited declines of 58.6% from a peak in 1907 (~321,000t) to 1971 (~133,000t) when the first herring fishing regulations came in, with a decline of 88.1% from 1907 to 1977 (~38,000t) when the total ban was introduced (Figure 2b). The herring fishing ban was lifted in 1981 for the west of Scotland and in 1983 for the North Sea. Since then (1983–2020), herring landings decreased by 12%, but landings of mackerel and blue whiting increased (Figure 2b).

FIGURE 1 | (a) landings by sector (% contribution to total Scottish landings by weight), (b) the relative contribution (%) of the top ten (out of twenty) fishing gears to total Scottish fisheries landings by weight. Data was not reported between 1995 and 1999.

3.4 | Demersal Fishing Gears

Passive gears (i.e., great/small lines) were dominant from 1890 to 1898 (contributing to 68.9% of demersal landings over this period); passive nets, such as gill/cod nets also landed small quantities of fish, contributing 0.1% of landings over this period (Figure 3a). During this time, the demersal fleet was largely steam powered (Figure 3a). Mobile gears outcompeted passive gears from 1899, with demersal (otter) trawlers landing 65.3% of demersal landings up to 1959 (Figure 3a). Line and passive misc nets landings, however, persisted within the fleet, albeit in decreasing quantities over time (e.g., line landings declined by 96.6% over the time-series) (Figure 3a). From the 1960s, motor power had overtaken steam in terms of derived landings, and trawl landings were superseded by

seine net landings (contributing 41% of demersal landings from 1960 to 1991). Landing by variants of demersal trawls also increased from the 1960s/70s, namely the industrial trawl (targeting predominantly Norway pout [*Trisopterus esmarkii*] and latterly sandeels [*Ammodytidae*]), pair trawl and light trawl, while demersal finfish were also taken by shellfish trawlers, potentially as bycatch (Figure 3a). Demersal trawlers contributed the most demersal landings again from 1992 to 2020 (62.6%) (Figure 3a).

3.4.1 | Demersal Fisheries

From 1890 to 1985, demersal landings (primarily cod, haddock [*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*] and whiting [*Merlangius merlangus*])

FIGURE 2 | (a) Total pelagic landings (tonnes) by each fishing gear, details annotated include dominant propulsion method (e.g., sail, steam, motor), war years (denoted by grey shaded areas), and periods where passive and mobile gears dominated. Data was not reported between 1995 and 1999; (b) species-specific pelagic landings (tonnes), key regulations and the collapse of North Sea herring spawning stock biomass (Corten 2013).

increased by 210.5% (Figure 3b). Landings of sandeels also increased rapidly from the mid-1970s, reaching nearly 63,000t in 1982, though landings fell to 0t in 2001 (Figure 3b). Ubiquitous declines in demersal landings were observed from 1985 to 2020, from ~295,000t to ~84,000t (decreasing by 71.5%) (Figure 3b). Over the time-series, some species landings increased: flatfish by 4%, saithe (*Pollachius virens*) by 25%, hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) by 237% and monkfish (*Lophius piscatorius*) by 1870%. Declines were observed in landings of haddock by 41%, skate and ray species by 46%, ling (*Molva molva*) by 52% and cod by 64%.

In the early 20th century regulations under the 'Trawling in Prohibited Areas Prevention Act, 1909' and the 'Sea Fishing Industry Act, 1933' were introduced though they had little noticeable impact on total landings (Figure 3b). TACs were introduced in 1975, fishing quotas were created under the CFP in 1983, vessel decommissioning schemes were introduced from 1994 to 2004, and Cod Recovery Zones were created in 2003,

covering North Sea, West of Scotland and Irish Sea fishing areas (Figure 3b).

3.5 | Shellfish Gears

Known passive gears (i.e., creels) dominated from 1890 to 1963, contributing to 23.3% of shellfish (i.e., crab and lobster) landings over this time (Figure 4). Most of the remaining shellfish over this period were landed by 'misc' gears (72.8%) (Figure 4). 'Misc' gears predominantly targeted mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) (Figure 4), which were likely harvested through hand collecting, raking and dredging (Mussel Beds In Tidal Waters (Scotland)—Resolution 1887).

From the mid-1950s, landings by mobile fishing gears (e.g., *Nephrops* trawls) gained momentum, overtaking creel landings in 1964 (Figure 4a). From 1964 to 2020, trawlers targeting

FIGURE 3 | (a) Total demersal landings (tonnes) by each fishing gear, details annotated include dominant propulsion method (e.g., steam, motor), war years (denoted by grey shaded areas), and periods where passive and mobile gears dominated. Data were not reported between 1995 and 1999; (b) species-specific demersal landings (tonnes), key regulations and the collapse of North Sea cod spawning stock biomass (2000–2007) (Beaugrand et al. 2022).

Nephrops prawns contributed 36.5% of shellfish landings, and dredgers targeting scallops contributed 29.4% (Figure 4). Key improvements to mobile gears included the introduction of the suction dredge in 1989 and twin *Nephrops* trawling in 1991 (Table 2). Passive gears, namely creels, continued to contribute substantially to shellfish landings from 1964 to 2020 (23.1%), while hand collection contributed 3.9% (Figure 4).

3.5.1 | Shellfish Fisheries

Shellfish contributed little to total reported Scottish landings from 1890 to 2020 (6.3%). Landings fluctuated on an overall downwards trajectory from 1892 to 1954, decreasing by 74.3% from ~19,000 to ~5000t (Figure 4b). Shellfish landings

then peaked in 2010 at ~68,000t (an increase of 1281.6%) as *Nephrops*, scallops and crabs were increasingly targeted (Figure 4b). The *Nephrops* TAC (2000) was introduced approximately 50years after the onset of *Nephrops* trawling (Figure 4). Shellfish landings declined to ~45,000t in 2020 as *Nephrops* and scallop landings declined, and crab landings stabilised (Figure 4b).

4 | Discussion

The historical transition from passive to mobile fishing gears is widely known but rarely quantified through time. This study finds that fundamental shifts in the way fishing gears interacted with their target species, as well as the environment (e.g., the

FIGURE 4 | (a) Total shellfish landings (tonnes) by each fishing gear, details annotated include war years (denoted by grey shaded areas), and periods where known passive and mobile gears dominated. Data were not reported between 1995 and 1999; (b) species-specific shellfish landings (tonnes) and key regulations.

seafloor), occurred rapidly across all sectors and were associated with increases in landings for variable periods after these transitions (Figures 2–4). In the demersal sector, line fishing landings were overshadowed by rising trawl landings from the late 1890s; in the pelagic sector, the 1960s marked the demise of traditional drift netting and the introduction of mobile pelagic gears (purse seines and pelagic trawls); in the shellfish sector, *Nephrops* trawlers dominated shellfish landings just 9 years after the method was first reported in 1955, overtaking creel landings (Figures 2–4). Gear transitions occurred at different times across sectors, which appears to be related to the expansion of opportunity but also in response to stock productivity declines (ICES 2022). Opportunities for the development and adoption of mobile gears, steam and motor engines and ancillary technologies resulted from wider socio-economic and political influences, for example, the Industrial Revolution, WW2, provision of financial assistance and market demands. These changes occurred long before any significant governance of fisheries took place.

The demise of traditional passive gears occurred earliest in Scotland's demersal fisheries (i.e., the decline of line fishing) (Figure 3). Rapid population growth, increased demand for affordable fish and the development of steam powered engines following the Industrial Revolution fuelled the rise of steam trawling effort from the late 19th century (J. R. Coull 1996), and increases in demersal landings ensued (Figure 3). Traditional beam trawls used from the early 19th century were improved in the latter 19th century as mechanised gear handling and otter boards enabled the use of much larger nets and allowed vessels to trawl over a greater diversity of terrain (Engelhard 2008; Knauss 2005; Montgomerie 2022). Steam engines also allowed for faster towing speeds, around the clock fishing and the expansion of trawling operations to productive offshore waters (Cook and Armstrong 1985; Roberts 2007). The 'Great Acceleration' of fisheries post-WW2 (1945–1975) was driven by a variety of factors: population expansion in the UK (improved post-war living conditions, high birth rates and falling death rates) led to increased demand for food, fishing

grounds had time to replenish after near cessation of fishing effort during the World War, and naval technologies were developed and adopted by the fishing industry (e.g., motor powered engines, synthetic twine, vessel positioning and fish finding technology) (Holm 2012; Table 2). New technologies, in addition to the development of seine netting and pair/industrial trawling across the 20th century (Figure 3a), facilitated the expansion of fishing operations and much increased catching efficiency. These developments led to increased landings of traditional target species, especially during the gadoid outburst in the 1960s (Figure 3). New fishing opportunities, for example, for industrial reduction species such as sandeels (rendered to fishmeal to feed growing aquaculture operations [Naylor et al. 2000]), also contributed to increasing demersal landings in the latter 20th century (Figure 3b). The steep decline in landings across a variety of demersal gear types from the 1980s (Figure 3a) was likely associated with the introduction of stricter fisheries regulations (e.g., under the CFP), vessel decommissioning schemes and reduced access to productive waters (e.g., around Iceland) after the introduction of EEZs (Table 2). However, it also illustrates the limits of technological innovation in extracting more fish when productivity limits have been reached or passed. The collapse of North Sea cod spawning stock biomass between 2000 and 2007 in response to long-term overfishing and adverse environmental conditions is testament to this (Beaugrand et al. 2022). Declining profitability of demersal fishing due to declines or collapses of main commercial target species, for example, cod, haddock and whiting (Scottish Government 2012) led to the continued decline of demersal landings across the 21st century (Figure 3), with many fishers shifting focus to shellfish, targeting primarily *Nephrops*.

In the pelagic sector, the decline and collapse of passive drift net landings, which had monopolised herring fisheries well into the 20th century (Figure 2), was largely due to reduced market outlets and demand following WW2 and latterly overfishing of herring (Whitmarsh et al. 1995). Sustained and increased fishing pressure for North Sea herring over the 20th century, combined with shifting environmental conditions due to reduced Atlantic inflow into the North Sea, ultimately led to recruitment failure between 1971 and 1979 and subsequently the collapse of the stock (Corten 2013). This led to major herring fishing restrictions in the 1970s (Figure 2b, Table 2), and the rapid adoption of several diverse new (motor powered) mobile fishing techniques (i.e., ring netting, pelagic trawling and purse-seining) from the 1960s/70s (Figure 2a) in a bid to capitalise on new fishing opportunities. For example, pelagic purse-seiners and trawlers shifted focus to mackerel and latterly blue whiting (Dickey-Collas et al. 2010; Figure 2b). Mackerel were targeted by purse-seiners mainly for reduction purposes (i.e., for fishmeal) in the 1960s. However, growing local/export demand from Europe, where mackerel was marketed as a low-cost alternative to dwindling herring supplies, led to increased targeting of mackerel by pelagic freezer trawlers (Dickey-Collas et al. 2010; ICES FishMap 2006). Furthermore, with the widespread adoption of echo sounding/sonar devices in the 1980s (Table 2), it became possible to locate and accurately target dense shoals of pelagic fish at any depth, hence leaving pelagic stocks with no refuges (Holm 2012; Montgomerie 2022; Valdemarsen 2001). Unsustainable exploitation of mackerel in the 1960s and 1970s

led to poor recruitment (ICES FishMap 2006), and landings declined sharply in the late 1990s (Figure 2b).

In the shellfish sector, it is likely that the transition to mobile gears in the 1960s and ensuing tripling of landings from 1970 to 2010 (Figure 4) reflected both the expansion and diversification of the lucrative export market for high value species such as lobsters, *Nephrops*, crabs and scallops (J. Coull 1997; Howard 2012; Mason and Fraser 1986; Scottish Government 2024), and as fishers were drawn to and transitioned to this largely unregulated sector. Only *Nephrops* were assigned catch limits in 2000, leading to a sharp but short-lived decline in landings between 2000 and 2000, and again from 2010 (Figure 4). Unlike in the demersal and pelagic industries, passive fishing methods (i.e., creel fishing) were not made redundant by the introduction of mobile gears (i.e., *Nephrops* trawls and dredges) due to distinctions between target species and their associated ranges (i.e., crabs predominantly targeted inshore by creels, *Nephrops* and scallops targeted predominantly offshore by trawls and dredges).

The passive to mobile gear transition came progressively later for the demersal, pelagic and shellfish sectors respectively (Figures 2–4), indicative of intensification of fishing effort for lower trophic level species through time. This phenomenon is well discussed in the literature and is associated with sequential depletion/collapse of stocks and addition of new fisheries (latterly with a focus on invertebrates) and is characteristic of intensively exploited regions, for example, the North Atlantic and Mediterranean (Colloca et al. 2017; Essington et al. 2006; Lotze 2007; Murawski 2000; Pauly et al. 1998; Pauly and Palomares 2001), but also reflects the development of new markets and fishing opportunities (J. Coull 1997).

In the UK and across Europe more broadly, several studies have highlighted the impacts of technological creep and associated increased fishing capacity, which rendered traditional fishing methods increasingly redundant and contributed to overexploitation, stock collapses, regime shifts and ecosystem degradation in the North Sea and North Atlantic (Kleiven et al. 2022; Le Floc'h et al. 2023; Lotze 2007; Thurstan et al. 2010). These trends are closely mirrored in the Northwest Atlantic (USA, Canada and Greenland) where groundfish fisheries primarily for cod were developed, using hook and line from the 16th century, cod traps and longlines in the late 1800s, and other trawls in the early 1900s (Hayes et al. 2025; Lear 1998). Fish filleting, quick-freezing and transport networks which enabled the distribution of landings to continental North America quickly facilitated expansion of fisheries exploitation (Lear 1998). As in Scotland, increasing fishing pressure enabled large catches in the mid-20th century but precipitous declines and collapse of cod stocks followed (Hayes et al. 2025; Lear 1998). Beyond the Atlantic, similar patterns have also been found. For example, in the Mediterranean, the size and fishing power of fleets grew progressively in the second half of the 20th century driven by technological progress, for example, widespread adoption of trawling, and resulted in the expansion of fisheries exploitation, increased landings and depletion of resources (Colloca et al. 2017; Maynou 2020). Marine fisheries in the Mediterranean have undergone a prolonged decline in productivity since the 1990s owing to chronic overexploitation as well as low investment in fleet advancement, sea warming,

pollution and invasive species and inadequate regulation (Colloca et al. 2017). In the South China Sea, post-WW2 rebuilding in the Philippines saw the mass motorisation of marine fisheries there, using salvaged motors from abandoned US military vehicles; meanwhile trawling technology was developed in Thailand in the 1960s and soon after in Malaysia, Singapore, Indonesia, Vietnam and China. Motorised trawling led to fisheries industrialisation, outcompeted traditional artisanal fisheries and ultimately led to overexploitation, resource depletion and increased focus on lower-trophic level species (Pauly and Liang 2020). These examples demonstrate this Scottish case study illustrates a pervasive process of innovation, displacement and resource depletion common to the evolution of most, if not all, global fisheries (Anticamara et al. 2011; Le Floch et al. 2023; Pauly et al. 2002; Pomeroy 2012; Valdemarsen 2001; Whitmarsh et al. 1995).

As the centre of the UK's commercial fishing sector (Akbari et al. 2022), Scotland plays a pivotal role in shaping national fisheries outputs. Consequently, challenges such as overexploitation and habitat degradation (from the transition to and intensification of fishing pressure by bottom-towed gears) have significant ramifications not only for fishery sustainability in the North Sea but also for the long-term resilience of the UK's marine ecosystems and coastal economies.

4.1 | Fisheries Management Flaws

Problems emerging from increasing fishing power received little attention in the narrative accounts examined until the late 20th century. Rather, for most of the period examined, fisheries policy actively encouraged technological innovation, fleet modernisation and increased capacity, for example, financial assistance made available by the Sea Fishing Industry Act and the Herring Industry Board to convert drift netting vessels to pelagic trawlers and seiners in the 1960s in response to declining herring yields (Le Floch et al. 2023; Standal 2005; Valdemarsen 2001; Whitmarsh et al. 1995). Increases in landings by pelagic trawlers and purse-seiners targeting mackerel, sprats and latterly blue whiting ensued (Figure 2). Scottish fisheries authorities had little incentive to impose controls over domestic fleets as by doing so would have meant foregoing their share of the common property resource (Whitmarsh et al. 1995). Whitmarsh et al. (1995) describe this predicament as a 'Prisoner's Dilemma', whereby limiting Scottish fishers at a time when other nations may not be exercising the same restraint would lead to these nations taking a larger share of local fish stocks. The prevailing and favoured policy over much of the 20th century thus centred around taking as much as possible while resources were available—an impetus for technological advancement (Whitmarsh et al. 1995).

Fishing bans and national or collaborative fisheries management regimes, that is, the EU Common Fisheries Policy and Exclusive Economic Zones were introduced in the 1970s and 1980s (Table 2), in response to signs of overfishing of key commercial stocks, such as herring, mackerel, cod, haddock, monkfish, whiting, saithe and plaice (Scottish Executive 2004). For herring fisheries, regulations were enacted within a decade of mobile gears/motor power becoming the dominant gear types/

propulsion mechanism, well illustrating the reactive tendencies of fisheries management to large-scale increases in fishing power (Figure 2). However, herring landings had already declined by 88% from a peak in 1907 up to when the fishing ban was introduced in 1977 (Figure 2). Similarly, cod landings had declined by 86% from a peak in 1912 up to 2003 when Cod Recovery Zones were created (Figure 3).

New policies led to the loss of open access fisheries, the introduction of quotas and licences, the decommissioning of vessels, the enforcement of technical regulations and restricted access to traditional fishing grounds (Department of Agriculture and Fisheries for Scotland 1981; Standal 2005). Concurrently, policies were centred around the maximum sustainable yield concept which led to a focus on individual species management rather than an ecosystem-based approach that accounts for multispecies fisheries and associations between fisheries (Legović et al. 2010), thus TACs were regularly set grossly too high to allow overfished stocks to begin to recover (Department of Agriculture and Fisheries for Scotland 1975; Proelss and Houghton 2012). Furthermore, pressure from trawling industries expedited the removal of the three-mile fishing limit in 1984 (Table 2), leading to the rapid onset of heavy fishing pressure on inshore demersal and shellfish stocks, in places initiating their near complete collapse (Thurstan and Roberts 2010).

Scotland's demersal fleet faced the strictest fishing quotas and restrictions (closed areas), and was the target of sequential vessel decommissioning schemes to reduce overcapacity and conserve vulnerable whitefish stocks, particularly cod; from 1993 to 2004 a total of 165 vessels over 10m in length (~7% of the fleet) were decommissioned (Scottish Executive 2006). Demersal landings (predominantly of haddock, cod and whiting) exhibited noticeable declines following the introduction of fishing quotas under the CFP in 1983 (declining by 71% up to 2020) and following successive vessel decommissioning schemes beginning in 1993 (declining by 55% up to 2020). Fishers were, however, able to capitalise on new fishing opportunities, diversifying their targets to higher or non-quota species. Landings of previously neglected demersal species such as monkfish increased by 300% from 1983 to 2020, and latterly landings of hake increased by 881% between 2002 and 2017 (Figure 3b).

The collapse of Newfoundland cod fishing mirrors experience in Scotland, and provides a cautionary tale of the severe ecological and economic consequences of failed management (Hayes et al. 2025). In the United States and Canada, similar fisheries management measures (closed areas and mesh size regulations) were instituted in the mid-20th century, but these were insufficient to control fishing pressure, and by the late 1960s, fleets were sequentially depleting stocks (e.g., cod, haddock, whiting, hake, mackerel and herring). Catch quotas and 200 mile fishing limits off the US coast were introduced in the early 1970s and a moratorium on cod fishing was established in 1992 (Hayes et al. 2025; Lear 1998). Despite this, Newfoundland cod has not substantially recovered (Hayes et al. 2025).

Scotland's pelagic and shellfish sectors became increasingly relevant following demersal fishing restrictions and overall declines in demersal landings (Figure 1). In the pelagic sector, landings increased following the introduction of the CFP,

with vessels targeting traditionally caught species (i.e., herring, which began to recover from collapse in the latter 20th century due to strict regulation [Dickey-Collas et al. 2010]) and increasingly targeting mackerel and latterly blue whiting (Figure 2). Shellfish landings also continued an upwards trajectory from the mid-1950s up to 2010.

Effective and sustainable fisheries management should be an iterative process that anticipates changes (e.g., to fishing capacity and the movement or decline of fish stocks due to changing environmental conditions) and adapts accordingly (Garcia and Ye 2018; Liu and Heino 2013). The ‘precautionary principle’ concept for fisheries management was framed in the 1990s and highlighted that to safeguard the marine environment from possibly damaging effects of the most destructive fishing practices and gears, a precautionary approach is necessary which may require action to control fishing activities before a causal link has been established by clear scientific evidence (Garcia 1994). Precautionary approaches in the form of protected areas, gear restrictions and zoning and temporal closures to protect marine ecosystems and allow replenishment of fish stocks have been widely accepted as beneficial to the environment and to fishery productivity and profitability (Leleu et al. 2012; Pita et al. 2011). Other anticipatory approaches include real-time closures and gear modifications or bans to reduce bycatch or high catches of juveniles (Garcia and Ye 2018; O’Keefe 2011), assessment of population dynamics and fish movement under climate change scenarios, thereby improving the ability of managers to assess stock status, determine sustainable yields and allocate fishing quotas for transboundary fish stocks (Liu and Heino 2013), and the setting of precautionary quotas in line with scientific advice (Fischer et al. 2021). Precautionary fisheries management strategies have not always been effective or accepted; for example, setting precautionary quotas for overfished species can lead to the redirection of effort and overfishing of new target species (Breen et al. 2016; Roberts et al. 2024). A study by Claydon and Calosso (2019) found that while fishers called for regulations to address problems evident in local fisheries, regulations designed to prevent problems that had not yet manifested were not popular, and instead were seen by fishers as punishment and as denying them of economic opportunities. More work aimed at improving understanding of drivers of effective governance frameworks is thus vital to tackle persistent problems related to resource overexploitation and ecological degradation (Roberts et al. 2024). In light of the failures of the EU Common Fisheries Policy to maintain and restore North Sea fish stocks (Proelss and Houghton 2012), future adoption of precautionary approaches to monitor/control increases in fishing capacity and minimise ecosystem impacts is of utmost importance.

4.2 | Can Technological Innovation Be a Force for Good?

In the latter 20th century, it became increasingly recognised that there were upper limits to growth in wild fish exploitation and awareness grew of the negative impacts of overfishing on fish stocks and the marine environment more broadly (Kennelly and Broadhurst 2002; Valdemarsen 2001). This helped induce a rise in consumer demand for premium priced sustainable, eco-labelled seafood (Squires and Vestergaard 2013). Increased awareness

has incentivised technological innovation and advancement directed towards reducing environmental impacts, for example, by improving the selectivity of gears to reduce bycatch and discards, and by modifying gears to minimise their side effects on habitats and fauna (Eigaard et al. 2014; Enever et al. 2022; Kennelly and Broadhurst 2002; Sala et al. 2023; Squires and Vestergaard 2013; Valdemarsen 2001). A review by Kennelly and Broadhurst (2021) identified trawl gear modifications to reduce bycatch, including raising otter boards and ground ropes using floats/rubber disks to reduce bycatch of benthic infauna and sea-floor impact, lights along the headline or ground rope to deter unwanted catches, increasing mesh sizes and changing mesh shapes to match the morphology of unwanted catches, and including mesh escape windows, sorting grids and guiding panels or deflectors to mitigate catches of non-target/undersized fish. Other studies have looked at reducing bycatch in longline fisheries by modifying bait types used (Gilman et al. 2020) and using circle rather than J-hooks (Squires and Vestergaard 2013), in gill net fisheries through the use of acoustic pingers and coloured netting (Eigaard et al. 2014), in shrimp trawling by incorporating turtle excluder devices (Tookes et al. 2023), and in scallop dredging by substituting illuminated pots (Enever et al. 2022). Scotland has made some headway to improve fishing selectivity and reduce bycatch; for example, square mesh escape panels were made mandatory for Scottish demersal trawl vessels in 2000 (Table 2). Technical gear modifications (sinking groundlines) have also been trialled in Scotland to reduce entanglement of marine megafauna in creel fisheries (Calderan et al. 2025). New ‘Smartrawl’ technology currently being tested in Scotland uses AI-technology to determine the sizes and species entering trawls using underwater cameras, and releases or retains the organism depending on whether it qualifies against a trawler’s intended catch using a computer-controlled gate, drastically improving the selectivity of trawl gears (Heriot-Watt University 2023).

Vessel monitoring using VMS (to track the location of fishing vessels) and Remote Electronic Monitoring (to monitor fishing operations in real time using cameras/sensors) has transformed the management and surveillance of fishing activity in Scotland to improve compliance with closed areas, recovery zones and fishing quotas, and to deter/prevent misreporting of landings and discards (Needle et al. 2015). More recent application of AI in fisheries monitoring and identification of illegal fishing, and in improving estimates of catch and bycatch through automated real-time catch analysis, also has the potential to improve the sustainable management of marine capture fisheries (Abangan et al. 2023; Kim et al. 2024; Wing and Woodward 2024). There are conflicting arguments as to whether recent advances in observation systems, for example, seabed imaging and artificial intelligence (AI) which provide greater insight into suitable fishing locations and fish behaviour (including interactions with gear) will maximise catches for the short term only and amplify ecosystem impacts (as past innovations documented here did) (Abangan et al. 2023), or whether such advances will enable data-informed decision making to reduce wider ecosystem damage as fishers can target stocks more precisely (Shedrawi et al. 2024). The latter will only be possible if there are improvements in regulation over historical experience.

Conservation-minded technological advancements could yet revolutionise how fisheries are conducted, monitored and

managed if government mandates or incentivises their adoption (Le Floc'h et al. 2023). Engaging fishers at all stages of technological development (e.g., from identification of selectivity issues through to the design and testing of new gears) is also pivotal (Cazé et al. 2022; Enever et al. 2022; Hall et al. 2007). Fishers provide expert local insight into fish-gear interactions, whether new technologies are practical, effective and compatible with existing methods, and are more likely to trust, adopt and correctly use new technologies when they participate in design and testing (Cazé et al. 2022; Hall et al. 2007; Kennelly and Broadhurst 2002; Suuronen 2022).

5 | Conclusion

Cases of overfishing and depletion of fish stocks globally have been well documented and are closely associated with technology-driven increases in catching power (Jackson et al. 2001; Scherrer and Galbraith 2020a). This study presents data on over a century of progressive technological innovation and advancement in Scottish fisheries following the onset of engine-powered industrial fishing in the late-19th century. It illuminates the expansion and abandonment of traditional fishing gears, quickly replaced by a diverse array of new mobile gears (equipped with ancillary technologies) with unprecedented fishing power to capitalise on declining and/or unfished resources. Adding to the pre-existing fishing effort of sail fishing craft, steam and motor-powered vessels were able to target fish stocks further offshore, soon reducing populations previously beyond the reach of fishing (Pauly et al. 2005). The spatial expansion and intensification of fishing both acted to mask, for a time, the progressive erosion of fish biomass in the North Sea and west of Scotland. However, the collapse of herring stocks in the 1970s (Corten 2013) and North Sea cod in the early 2000s (Beaugrand et al. 2022) exemplify how productivity limits for key commercially targeted species were eventually breached. The sequential acquisition of more effective mobile and destructive gears in the demersal, pelagic and shellfish sectors respectively raises fundamental questions about the integrity of local marine ecosystems and the viable persistence of current fishing industries which are becoming increasingly reliant on few largely unregulated shellfish stocks.

Technological progress was facilitated and encouraged by fisheries governing bodies over much of the 20th century, which allowed for heavy investment into the industry and permitted fisheries to remain profitable in the face of fish stock declines. However, such investment failed to ensure long-term sustainability and, in fact, undermined it. To break this cycle of innovation driven overfishing, regulatory efforts to restrict capacity and reduce the environmental impacts of fishing gears must in future be anticipatory and continually strengthened as long as catching power in a fishery continues to increase to ensure the future of local fishing industries, the supply of wild-caught fish and the resilience and integrity of marine ecosystems.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in Figshare using the identifier: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28649099>.

References

- Abangan, A. S., D. Kopp, and R. Faillettaz. 2023. "Artificial Intelligence for Fish Behavior Recognition May Unlock Fishing Gear Selectivity." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 10: 1010761. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1010761>.
- Abernethy, K. E., P. Trebilcock, B. Kebede, E. H. Allison, and N. K. Dulvy. 2010. "Fuelling the Decline in UK Fishing Communities?" *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 67, no. 5: 1076–1085. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsp289>.
- Akbari, N., T. Bjørndal, P. Failler, A. Forse, M. H. Taylor, and B. Drakeford. 2022. "A Multi-Criteria Framework for the Sustainable Management of Fisheries: A Case Study of UK's North Sea Scottish Fisheries." *Environmental Management* 70, no. 1: 79–96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-022-01607-w>.
- Anticamara, J. A., R. Watson, A. Gelchu, and D. Pauly. 2011. "Global Fishing Effort (1950–2010): Trends, Gaps, and Implications." *Fisheries Research* 107, no. 1: 131–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2010.10.016>.
- Atwood, T. B., A. Romanou, T. DeVries, et al. 2024. "Atmospheric CO₂ Emissions and Ocean Acidification From Bottom-Trawling." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 10: 1125137. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1125137>.
- Beaugrand, G., A. Balembois, L. Kléparski, and R. R. Kirby. 2022. "Addressing the Dichotomy of Fishing and Climate in Fishery Management With the FishClim Model." *Communications Biology* 5, no. 1: 1146. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-04100-6>.
- Breen, B., H. Kelley, and S. Hynes. 2016. "The Impact of Precautionary Quota Constraints on the Composition of Multispecies Harvest Portfolios." *Marine Policy* 69: 13–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.10.006>.
- Calderan, S., B. Cisternino, M. De Noia, R. Leaper, E. MacLennan, and B. Philp. 2025. "Successful Collaborative Trials of Simple Gear Modifications to Reduce Entanglement of Whales and Other Megafauna in Scotland's Static Pot (Creel) Fisheries." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 82, no. 6: fsae157. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsae157>.
- Cazé, C., J. Réveillias, A. Danto, and C. Mazé. 2022. "Integrating Fishers' Knowledge Contributions in Marine Science to Tackle Bycatch in the Bay of Biscay." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 9: 1071163. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1071163>.
- Claydon, J., and M. Calosso. 2019. "Proactive (and Reactive) Management of Fishery Resources in the Turks and Caicos Islands Gestión Proactiva y Reactiva de los Recursos Pesqueros en las Islas Turcas y Caicos Gestion Proactive et Réactive des Ressources Halieutiques Dans les Îles Turcs et Caicos." *68th Proceedings of the 68th Gulf and Caribbean Fisheries Institute*.

- Colloca, F., G. Scarcella, and S. Libralato. 2017. "Recent Trends and Impacts of Fisheries Exploitation on Mediterranean Stocks and Ecosystems." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 4: 244. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00244>.
- Cook, R. M., and D. W. Armstrong. 1985. "Changes in Catchability of Cod, Haddock, and Whiting Associated With the Scottish Seine-Net Fleet." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 42, no. 2: 171–178. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/42.2.171>.
- Corten, A. 2013. "Recruitment Depressions in North Sea Herring." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 70, no. 1: 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fss187>.
- Coull, J. 1997. "Shell Fisheries in Scotland: A Case of Transition From Low to High Value." *Scottish Geographical Magazine* 113, no. 3: 168–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00369229718737010>.
- Coull, J. R. 1996. *The Sea Fisheries of Scotland: A Historical Geography*. John Donald Publishers.
- Day, E. E. D. 1969. "The British Sea Fishing Industry." *Geography* 54, no. 2: 165–180.
- Department of Agriculture and Fisheries for Scotland. 1975. *Fisheries of Scotland Report for 1974 (Including Fisheries Research Report)*. Department of Agriculture and Fisheries for Scotland.
- Department of Agriculture and Fisheries for Scotland. 1981. *Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistical Tables 1980*. Department of Agriculture and Fisheries for Scotland.
- Dickey-Collas, M., R. D. M. Nash, T. Brunel, et al. 2010. "Lessons Learned From Stock Collapse and Recovery of North Sea Herring: A Review." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 67, no. 9: 1875–1886. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsq033>.
- Eigaard, O. R., P. Marchal, H. Gislason, and A. D. Rijnsdorp. 2014. "Technological Development and Fisheries Management." *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture* 22, no. 2: 156–174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2014.899557>.
- Enever, R., P. D. Doherty, J. Ashworth, et al. 2022. "Scallop Potting With Lights: A Novel, Low Impact Method for Catching European King Scallop (*Pecten maximus*)." *Fisheries Research* 252: 106334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2022.106334>.
- Engelhard, G. H. 2008. "One Hundred and Twenty Years of Change in Fishing Power of English North Sea Trawlers." In *Advances in Fisheries Science*, 1–25. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/978144302653.ch1>.
- Engelhard, G. H. 2016. "On the Need to Study Fishing Power Change: Challenges and Perspectives." In *Perspectives on Oceans Past*, edited by K. Schwerdtner Máñez and B. Poulsen, 89–101. Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-7496-3_6.
- Engelhard, G. H., D. A. Righton, and J. K. Pinnegar. 2014. "Climate Change and Fishing: A Century of Shifting Distribution in North Sea Cod." *Global Change Biology* 20, no. 8: 2473–2483. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12513>.
- Essington, T. E., A. H. Beaudreau, and J. Wiedenmann. 2006. "Fishing Through Marine Food Webs." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 103, no. 9: 3171–3175. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0510964103>.
- Fischer, S. H., J. A. A. De Oliveira, J. D. Mumford, and L. T. Kell. 2021. "Application of Explicit Precautionary Principles in Data-Limited Fisheries Management." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 78, no. 8: 2931–2942. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsab169>.
- Garcia, S. M. 1994. "The Precautionary Principle: Its Implications in Capture Fisheries Management." *Ocean and Coastal Management* 22, no. 2: 99–125. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0964-5691\(94\)90014-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0964-5691(94)90014-0).
- Garcia, S. M., and Y. Ye. 2018. *Rebuilding of Marine Fisheries Part 2: Case Studies (Technical Paper 630/2)*. FAO. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/5bafded4-f48a-4b63-8b38-e7745dc5ce3/content>.
- Garstang, W. 1900. "The Impoverishment of the Sea. A Critical Summary of the Experimental and Statistical Evidence Bearing Upon the Alleged Depletion of the Trawling Grounds." *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 6, no. 1: 1–69. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315400072374>.
- Gilman, E., M. Chaloupka, P. Bach, et al. 2020. "Effect of Pelagic Longline Bait Type on Species Selectivity: A Global Synthesis of Evidence." *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries* 30, no. 3: 535–551. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-020-09612-0>.
- Gislason, H. 1994. "Ecosystem Effects of Fishing Activities in the North Sea." *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 29, no. 6: 520–527. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-326X\(94\)90680-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-326X(94)90680-7).
- Hall, M. A., H. Nakano, S. Clarke, et al. 2007. "Working With Fishers to Reduce By-Catches." In *By-Catch Reduction in the World's Fisheries*, edited by S. J. Kennelly, 235–288. Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-6078-6_8.
- Hall-Spencer, J. M., and P. G. Moore. 2000. "Scallop Dredging Has Profound, Long-Term Impacts on Maerl Habitats." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 57, no. 5: 1407–1415. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmsc.2000.0918>.
- Hatcher, A., and A. Read. 2001. "Fishing Rights and Structural Changes in the UK Fishing Industry." In *Case Studies on the Effects of Transferable Fishing Rights on Fleet Capacity and Concentration of Quota Ownership*, edited by R. Shotton, 1–14. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://www.fao.org/4/Y2498E/y2498e02.htm>.
- Hayes, P., P. Holm, and J. Nicholls. 2025. "500 Years of the Once Largest Fishery in the World: A Comprehensive Catch Reconstruction for the Newfoundland Cod Fishery (1508–2023)." *Fisheries Research* 285: 107325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2025.107325>.
- Heriot-Watt University. 2023. *AI-Empowered Fishing Net to Help Prevent Marine Bycatch*. Heriot-Watt University. <https://www.hw.ac.uk/news/2023/ai-empowered-fishing-net-to-help-prevent-marine-bycatch>.
- Holm, P. 2012. "World War II and the 'Great Acceleration' of North Atlantic Fisheries." *Global Environment* 5, no. 10: 67. <https://doi.org/10.3197/ge.2012.051005>.
- Howard, P. M. 2012. "Sharing or Appropriation? Share Systems, Class and Commodity Relations in Scottish Fisheries." *Journal of Agrarian Change* 12, no. 2–3: 316–343. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-0366.2011.00355.x>.
- Hunt, G. L., G. H. Engelhard, J. K. Pinnegar, B. D. Wigham, and N. V. C. Polunin. 2024. "Trawling Through Time: Reconstructing a Late Nineteenth Century Beam Trawl for Scientific Inshore Fishery Investigations." *Maritime Studies* 23, no. 3: 33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40152-024-00371-3>.
- ICES. 2022. "Greater North Sea Ecoregion—Fisheries Overview [Report]." ICES Advice: Fisheries Overviews. <https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.advice.21641360.v1>.
- ICES FishMap. 2006. "Mackerel." ICES. <https://www.ices.dk/about-ICES/projects/EU-RFP/EU%20Repository/ICES%20FishMap/ICES%20FishMap%20species%20factsheet-mackerel.pdf>.
- Jackson, J. B., M. X. Kirby, W. H. Berger, et al. 2001. "Historical Overfishing and the Recent Collapse of Coastal Ecosystems." *Science* 293, no. 5530: 629–637. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1059199>.
- Jones, P. 2016. "Technological Innovation and Resource Management in the Fisheries of the British Isles, ca. 1400–1900." PhD, University of Strathclyde. <https://stax.strath.ac.uk/concern/theses/nk322d37w>.
- Jones, P., A. Cathcart, and D. C. Speirs. 2015. "Early Evidence of the Impact of Preindustrial Fishing on Fish Stocks From the Mid-West and Southeast Coastal Fisheries of Scotland in the 19th Century." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 73, no. 5: 1404–1414. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsv189>.

- Kennelly, S. J., and M. K. Broadhurst. 2002. "By-Catch Begone: Changes in the Philosophy of Fishing Technology." *Fish and Fisheries* 3, no. 4: 340–355. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1467-2979.2002.00090.x>.
- Kennelly, S. J., and M. K. Broadhurst. 2021. "A Review of Bycatch Reduction in Demersal Fish Trawls." *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries* 31, no. 2: 289–318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-021-09644-0>.
- Kerby, T. K., W. W. L. Cheung, and G. H. Engelhard. 2012. "The United Kingdom's Role in North Sea Demersal Fisheries: A Hundred Year Perspective." *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries* 22, no. 3: 621–634. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-012-9261-y>.
- Kim, S.-G., S.-H. Lee, and T.-H. Im. 2024. "AI-RCAS: A Real-Time Artificial Intelligence Analysis System for Sustainable Fisheries Management." *Sustainability* 16, no. 18: 8178. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16188178>.
- Kleiven, A. R., S. H. Espeland, S. Stiansen, K. Ono, F. Zimmermann, and E. M. Olsen. 2022. "Technological Creep Masks Continued Decline in a Lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) Fishery Over a Century." *Scientific Reports* 12, no. 1: 3318. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-07293-2>.
- Knauss, J. M. 2005. "The Growth of British Fisheries During the Industrial Revolution." *Ocean Development & International Law* 36, no. 1: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00908320490508912>.
- Le Floc'h, P., M. Merzéréraud, J. Beckenstein, et al. 2023. "Explaining Technical Change and Its Impacts Over the Very Long Term: The Case of the Atlantic Sardine Fishery in France From 1900 to 2017." *Research Policy* 52, no. 9: 104864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2023.104864>.
- Lear, W. H. 1998. "History of Fisheries in the Northwest Atlantic: The 500-Year Perspective." *Journal of Northwest Atlantic Fishery Science* 23: 41–73.
- Legović, T., J. Klanjšček, and S. Geček. 2010. "Maximum Sustainable Yield and Species Extinction in Ecosystems." *Ecological Modelling* 221, no. 12: 1569–1574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2010.03.024>.
- Leleu, K., F. Alban, D. Pelletier, E. Charbonnel, Y. Letourneur, and C. F. Boudouresque. 2012. "Fishers' Perceptions as Indicators of the Performance of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)." *Marine Policy* 36, no. 2: 414–422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2011.06.002>.
- Liu, X., and M. Heino. 2013. "Comparing Proactive and Reactive Management: Managing A Transboundary Fish Stock Under Changing Environment." *Natural Resource Modeling* 26, no. 4: 480. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nrm.12009>.
- Longo, S. B., R. Clausen, and B. Clark. 2015. *The Tragedy of the Commodity: Oceans, Fisheries, and Aquaculture*. Rutgers University Press.
- Lotze, H. K. 2007. "Rise and Fall of Fishing and Marine Resource Use in the Wadden Sea, Southern North Sea." *Fisheries Research* 87, no. 2: 208–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2006.12.009>.
- Mahévas, S., Y. Vermard, T. Hutton, et al. 2011. "An Investigation of Human vs. Technology-Induced Variation in Catchability for a Selection of European Fishing Fleets." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 68, no. 10: 2252–2263. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsr150>.
- Marchal, P., B. Andersen, B. Caillart, et al. 2007. "Impact of Technological Creep on Fishing Effort and Fishing Mortality, for a Selection of European Fleets." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 64, no. 1: 192–209. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsl014>.
- Mason, J., and D. I. Fraser. 1986. "Shellfish Fisheries in the Clyde Sea Area." *Proceedings of the Royal Society of Edinburgh, Section B: Biological Sciences* 90: 439–450. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0269727000005145>.
- Maynou, F. 2020. "Evolution of Fishing Capacity in a Mediterranean Fishery in the First Two Decades of the 21st c." *Ocean and Coastal Management* 192: 105190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2020.105190>.
- Montgomerie, M. 2022. *Basic Fishing Methods: A Comprehensive Guide to Commercial Fishing Methods*. SEAFISH. <https://www.seafish.org/document/?id=9f2fcd97-8bef-4c28-9185-b219b8eedf8a>.
- Murawski, S. A. 2000. "Definitions of Overfishing From an Ecosystem Perspective." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 57, no. 3: 649–658. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmsc.2000.0738>.
- Mussel Beds In Tidal Waters (Scotland)—Resolution. 1887. "House of Commons." [https://hansard.parliament.uk/Commons/1887-05-12/debates/90383c78-6ed1-4d44-8e43-c221662e6430/MusselBedsInTidalWaters\(Scotland\)%E2%80%94Resolution](https://hansard.parliament.uk/Commons/1887-05-12/debates/90383c78-6ed1-4d44-8e43-c221662e6430/MusselBedsInTidalWaters(Scotland)%E2%80%94Resolution).
- Naylor, R. L., R. J. Goldburg, J. H. Primavera, et al. 2000. "Effect of Aquaculture on World Fish Supplies." *Nature* 405, no. 6790: 1017–1024. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35016500>.
- Needle, C. L., R. Dinsdale, T. B. Buch, R. M. D. Catarino, J. Drewery, and N. Butler. 2015. "Scottish Science Applications of Remote Electronic Monitoring." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 72, no. 4: 1214–1229. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsu225>.
- O'Keefe, C. E. 2011. "The Advantages of Proactive Management Over Reactive Regulations for Implementing Accountability in the US Sea Scallop Fishery." *Annual Science Conference*. <https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.pub.25039364.v1>.
- Palomares, M., and D. Pauly. 2019. "On the Creeping Increase of Vessels' Fishing Power." *Ecology and Society* 24, no. 3: 31. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-11136-240331>.
- Pauly, D., V. Christensen, J. Dalsgaard, R. Froese, and F. Torres. 1998. "Fishing Down Marine Food Webs." *Science* 279, no. 5352: 860–863. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.279.5352.860>.
- Pauly, D., V. Christensen, S. Guénette, et al. 2002. "Towards Sustainability in World Fisheries." *Nature* 418, no. 6898: 689–695. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01017>.
- Pauly, D., and C. Liang. 2020. "The Fisheries of the South China Sea: Major Trends Since 1950." *Marine Policy* 121: 103584. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103584>.
- Pauly, D., and M. L. D. Palomares. 2001. "Fishing Down Marine Food Webs: An Update." In *Waters in Peril*, edited by L. Bendell-Young and P. Gallagher, 47–56. Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-1493-0_4.
- Pauly, D., R. Watson, and J. Alder. 2005. "Global Trends in World Fisheries: Impacts on Marine Ecosystems and Food Security." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society, B: Biological Sciences* 360, no. 1453: 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2004.1574>.
- Payne, A. I. L., J. Cotter, and T. Potter. 2009. *Advances in Fisheries Science: 50 Years on From Beverton and Holt*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Pita, C., G. J. Pierce, I. Theodossiou, and K. Macpherson. 2011. "An Overview of Commercial Fishers' Attitudes Towards Marine Protected Areas." *Hydrobiologia* 670, no. 1: 289–306. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-011-0665-9>.
- Pomeroy, R. S. 2012. "Managing Overcapacity in Small-Scale Fisheries in Southeast Asia." *Marine Policy* 36, no. 2: 520–527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2011.10.002>.
- Pontecorvo, G., and W. E. Schrank. 2012. "The Expansion, Limit and Decline of the Global Marine Fish Catch." *Marine Policy* 36, no. 5: 1178–1181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2012.03.005>.
- Porz, L., W. Zhang, N. Christiansen, J. Kossack, U. Daewel, and C. Schrum. 2024. "Quantification and Mitigation of Bottom-Trawling Impacts on Sedimentary Organic Carbon Stocks in the North Sea." *Biogeosciences* 21, no. 10: 2547–2570. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-21-2547-2024>.
- Proelss, A., and K. Houghton. 2012. "The EU Common Fisheries Policy in Light of the Precautionary Principle." *Ocean and Coastal Management* 70: 22–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2012.05.015>.
- Read, A. J., P. Drinker, and S. Northridge. 2006. "Bycatch of Marine Mammals in U.S. and Global Fisheries." *Conservation Biology* 20, no. 1: 163–169. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2006.00338.x>.

- Rihan, D., N. Bailey, and H. Doerner. 2016. "Reports of the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF): Evaluation of the Landing Obligation Joint Recommendations (STECF 16 10)." Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF). <https://doi.org/10.2788/59074>.
- Roberts, C. 2007. *The Unnatural History of the Sea*. Island Press.
- Roberts, C., C. Béné, N. Bennett, et al. 2024. "Rethinking Sustainability of Marine Fisheries for a Fast-Changing Planet." *NPI Ocean Sustainability* 3, no. 1: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44183-024-00078-2>.
- Sala, A., J. Depestele, A. Gümüş, et al. 2023. "Technological Innovations to Reduce the Impact of Bottom Gears on the Seabed." *Marine Policy* 157: 105861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105861>.
- Sala, E., and N. Knowlton. 2006. "Global Marine Biodiversity Trends." *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 31, no. 1: 93–122. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.energy.31.020105.100235>.
- Scherrer, K., and E. Galbraith. 2020a. "Regulation Strength and Technology Creep Play Key Roles in Global Long-Term Projections of Wild Capture Fisheries." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 77, no. 7–8: 2518–2528. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsaa109>.
- Scherrer, K., and E. Galbraith. 2020b. "The Risk of Underestimating Long-Term Fisheries Creep." *Ecology and Society* 25, no. 1: 18. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-11389-250118>.
- Scottish Executive. 2004. *Scottish Fisheries Statistics 2003*. Scottish Executive. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/statistics/2020/11/sea-fisheries-statistics-1922-2010/documents/2003/2003/govscot%3Adocument/2003.pdf>.
- Scottish Executive. 2006. *Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistics 2005*. Scottish Executive. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/statistics/2020/11/sea-fisheries-statistics-1922-2010/documents/2005/2005/govscot%3Adocument/2005.pdf>.
- Scottish Government. 2011. "Sea Fisheries Statistics 1922–2010." <http://www.gov.scot/publications/sea-fisheries-statistics-1922-2010/>.
- Scottish Government. 2012. *Scottish Marine and Freshwater Science: Clyde Ecosystem Review*. Scottish Government. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-marine-freshwater-science-volume-3-number-3-clyde-ecosystem/pages/6/>.
- Scottish Government. 2024. *Scottish Sea Fisheries Statistics 2023*. Scottish Government. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/statistics/2024/12/scottish-sea-fisheries-statistics-2023/documents/scottish-sea-fisheries-statistics-2023/scottish-sea-fisheries-statistics-2023/govscot%3Adocument/Scottish%2BSea%2BFisheries%2BStatistics%2B2023.pdf>.
- Shedrawi, G., F. Magron, B. Vigga, et al. 2024. "Leveraging Deep Learning and Computer Vision Technologies to Enhance Management of Coastal Fisheries in the Pacific Region." *Scientific Reports* 14, no. 1: 20915. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-71763-y>.
- Squires, D., and N. Vestergaard. 2013. "Technical Change in Fisheries." *Marine Policy* 42: 286–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2013.03.019>.
- Standal, D. 2005. "Nuts and Bolts in Fisheries Management—A Technological Approach to Sustainable Fisheries?" *Marine Policy* 29, no. 3: 255–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2004.04.004>.
- Stewart, B. D., and L. M. Howarth. 2016. "Chapter 14—Quantifying and Managing the Ecosystem Effects of Scallop Dredge Fisheries." In *Developments in Aquaculture and Fisheries Science*, edited by S. E. Shumway and G. J. Parsons, vol. 40, 585–609. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-62710-0.00018-3>.
- Suuronen, P. 2022. "Understanding Perspectives and Barriers That Affect Fishers' Responses to Bycatch Reduction Technologies." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 79, no. 4: 1015–1023. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsac045>.
- Symes, D. 2001. "The Future of Europe's Fisheries: Towards a 2020 Vision." *Geography* 86, no. 4: 318–328.
- Thurstan, R. H., S. Brockington, and C. M. Roberts. 2010. "The Effects of 118 Years of Industrial Fishing on UK Bottom Trawl Fisheries." *Nature Communications* 1, no. 1: 15. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms1013>.
- Thurstan, R. H., H. McCormick, J. Preston, et al. 2024. "Records Reveal the Vast Historical Extent of European Oyster Reef Ecosystems." *Nature Sustainability* 7, no. 12: 1719–1729. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-024-01441-4>.
- Thurstan, R. H., and C. M. Roberts. 2010. "Ecological Meltdown in the Firth of Clyde, Scotland: Two Centuries of Change in a Coastal Marine Ecosystem." *PLoS One* 5, no. 7: e11767. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0011767>.
- Tookes, J. S., T. Yandle, and B. Fluech. 2023. "The Role of Fisher Engagement in the Acceptance of Turtle Excluder Devices in Georgia's Shrimping Industry." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 80, no. 3: 407–416. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsac062>.
- UK Parliamentary Papers. n.d. Retrieved April 11, 2024. <https://parlipapers.proquest.com/parlipapers/search/basic/hcpcbsearch>.
- Valdemarsen, J. W. 2001. "Technological Trends in Capture Fisheries." *Ocean and Coastal Management* 44, no. 9: 635–651. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0964-5691\(01\)00073-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0964-5691(01)00073-4).
- Walsh, S. J., and P. Winger. 2011. "Bottom Seining in Canada, 1948–2010: Its Development, Fisheries and Ecosystem Impacts." Canadian Technical Report of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences, 2922.
- Waterman, J. J. 1964. "Measures, Stowage Rates and Yields of Fishery Products: Issue 17 of Torry Advisory Note." Torry Research Station. <https://www.fao.org/3/x5898e/x5898e01.htm#Measures%20of%20weight%20and%20volume>.
- Watling, L., and E. A. Norse. 1998. "Disturbance of the Seabed by Mobile Fishing Gear: A Comparison to Forest Clearcutting." *Conservation Biology* 12, no. 6: 1180–1197. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1739.1998.0120061180.x>.
- Whitmarsh, D. J., C. A. Reid, C. Gulvin, and M. R. Dunn. 1995. "Natural Resource Exploitation and the Role of New Technology: A Case-History of the UK Herring Industry." *Environmental Conservation* 22, no. 2: 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892900010146>.
- Wing, K., and B. Woodward. 2024. "Advancing Artificial Intelligence in Fisheries Requires Novel Cross-Sector Collaborations." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 81, no. 10: 1912–1919. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsae118>.
- Woll, A. K., and M. Ålesund. 2006. "The Edible Crab. Biology—Grading—Handling Live Crabs." The Fishery and Aquaculture Industry Research Fund.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Appendix S1:** faf70050-sup-0001-AppendixS1.docx. **Appendix S2:** faf70050-sup-0002-AppendixS2.docx. **Appendix S3:** faf70050-sup-0003-AppendixS3.docx.